

Assessing the quality and results of meta-analyses on crop diversification Protocol for systematic review and evidence map

Damien Beillouin, Tamara Ben-Ari, David Makoswki

► To cite this version:

Damien Beillouin, Tamara Ben-Ari, David Makoswki. Assessing the quality and results of meta-analyses on crop diversification Protocol for systematic review and evidence map. 2018. hal-01815485

HAL Id: hal-01815485

<https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01815485>

Preprint submitted on 14 Jun 2018

HAL is a multi-disciplinary open access archive for the deposit and dissemination of scientific research documents, whether they are published or not. The documents may come from teaching and research institutions in France or abroad, or from public or private research centers.

L'archive ouverte pluridisciplinaire **HAL**, est destinée au dépôt et à la diffusion de documents scientifiques de niveau recherche, publiés ou non, émanant des établissements d'enseignement et de recherche français ou étrangers, des laboratoires publics ou privés.

Assessing the quality and results of meta-analyses
on crop diversification
Protocol for systematic review and evidence map

Damien Beillouin, Tamara Ben-Ari, David Makoswki *

June 2018

*UMR Agronomie, INRA, AgroParisTech, Université Paris-Saclay, Thiverval-Grignon, France
Contact: damien.beillouin@inra.fr

Contents

- 1 Background** **3**
- 2 Objective of the review** **3**
- 3 Protocol** **4**
 - 3.1 Literature search 4
 - 3.1.1 Databases screened 4
 - 3.1.2 Internet engine searches 4
 - 3.1.3 Testing for performance of the search 4
 - 3.1.4 Search terms, languages and restrictions 4
 - 3.2 Inclusion criteria and article screening 5
 - 3.2.1 Study inclusion and exclusion criteria 5
 - 3.2.2 Screening 5
 - 3.3 Data extraction and analyses 6
 - 3.3.1 Characteristics of the meta-analysis, potential effect modifiers and sources of heterogeneity 6
 - 3.3.2 Study quality assessment 6
 - 3.3.3 Effect size and meta-regressors 6
 - 3.3.4 Data extraction strategy 6
- 4 Data synthesis and presentation** **6**
- 5 Declaration** **6**
- 6 Supplementary file: list of pre-identified meta-analyses** **7**

Abstract

Diversified agriculture is often presented as a major lever to improve the sustainability of agroecosystems. Of particular interest, is the productivity and economic performance of these systems as well as the associated environmental impacts. A multifunctional assessment of the potential benefits of diversified agriculture is thus essential. Several meta-analyses synthesized scientific evidence regarding one or a small number of crop diversification management on one or more types of impact.

Yet, to date, no study has attempted to provide a comprehensive systematic synthesis of the results of these meta-analyses. We present here a literature search protocol for the collection, evaluation and description of all meta-analyses on all forms of crop diversification and all performance criteria.

The protocol relies on the use of six bibliographic databases and grey literature sources without any date restriction. Only meta-analyses comparing diversification strategies to less diversified systems are considered.

The quality of each selected meta-analysis is analyzed. A searchable database containing extracted meta-data, quality criteria and measured effect sizes is built.

Keywords— systematic review, crop diversification, catch crop, agroforestry, species mixture, rotation, cover crops, intercropping, buffer strips, trap crops

1 Background

Diversified agricultural production systems include a wide range of practices aiming at incorporating agrobiodiversity across multiple spatial and/or temporal scales (Altieri and Nicholls, 2004; Kremen and Miles, 2012; Lin, 2011; Tomich et al., 2011). The strategies of crop diversification are numerous and often intertwined. At the field scale, crop diversification for example refers to mixes of varieties (e.g. Lin 2011), mixes of annual and perennial crops (e.g. Bayala et al. 2018), the placement of buffer strips within or around the fields (e.g. Chen et al. 2016), or alternating crops (e.g. cover crop, intercropping and rotation – Cernay et al. 2017). At the landscape scale, diversification can be achieved through the integration of functions other than production such as, natural habitat and fallow land (Altieri, 1999; Gurr et al., 2003).

The diversification of cropping systems is generally considered to improve the resilience or more broadly, the sustainability of agroecosystems (Aguilar et al., 2015; Gaudin et al., 2015; Kremen and Miles, 2012; Lin, 2011; Tengö and Belfrage, 2004). Numerous individual studies quantified the agronomic, economic, or environmental impacts of crop diversification. Over 30,000 articles have been published on this topic between 1945 and February 2018 in agronomy field journals¹. Several systematic reviews (see the provisional list of 16 meta-analyses in the Supplementary files) have synthesized results provided by these individual studies. The meta-analyses focused on one or several strategies of crop diversification (e.g. Letourneau et al. 2011) on the impact of introducing flowers in or around crop fields on enemy abundance, parasitism and crop damage; Miguez and Bollero (2005) on the effects of catch crops on crop productivity).

An up to date and comprehensive agronomic, economic, and environmental assessment of impacts of crop diversification has still not been conducted. A systematic literature review and a comprehensive synthesis of studies is an effective way to weight to-date evidences and identify research gaps. Results of meta-analyses can be synthesized qualitatively or quantitatively. The latter option poses a series of challenges, such as the aggregation of highly heterogeneous results and measures of impacts, the potential presence of low quality meta-analyses, and the redundancy of individual studies among meta-analyses. To make progress we rely on an exhaustive literature search to build databases integrating a quality assessment of each meta-analysis, meta-data, strategies of crop diversification and type of output analyzed. We also report the effect size and characteristics of individual studies included in each meta-analysis.

2 Objective of the review

Our general objective is to collect and describe all meta-analyses assessing the agronomic, economic, and environmental impacts of any strategies of crop diversification worldwide.

Three databases are obtained:

1. A database including a comprehensive quality assessment of each meta-analyses using standard criteria.
2. A database detailing the characteristics of the cropping systems, the strategies of crop diversification and the type of impacts analyzed in each meta-analysis.

¹Search on web of sciences, the 23 April 2018. Equation: (cropping system OR crop* OR agriculture) AND ((rotation OR Diversification OR intercrop* OR cover crop OR mixture) OR agroforestry OR agroecology), Web of science categories: Agronomy or soil science, plant science, environmental science, agriculture multidisciplinary; Timespan: All years

We aim at identifying:

- The types of economic, environmental, and production impacts considered in the individual meta-analyses*
 - The types of crop production systems considered*
 - The geographical areas where individual studies were conducted*
 - The knowledge gaps*
3. A database on the comprehensive synthesis of impacts of crop diversification (i.e., all effect-sizes computed in each individual meta-analyses are collected)

The data bases associated with the three objectives will be fully accessible online at no cost.

3 Protocol

3.1 Literature search

3.1.1 Databases screened

The five following databases, which cover natural and social sciences are considered:

- Thomson Reuters (formerly ISI) Web of Science, New York, USA, <http://apps.webofknowledge.com>
- CAB abstracts, CABI, Wallingford, United Kingdom, <http://www.cabdirect.org/>
- Greenfile, EBSCO, Massachusetts, <http://www.greeninfoonline.com/>
- Environment Complete Database, EBSCO, Massachusetts, <https://www.ebsco.com/>
- Agricola (AGRICultural OnLine Access) database, National Agricultural Library (NAL) USA - <http://agricola.nal.usda.gov/>

3.1.2 Internet engine searches

Google Scholar (<http://www.scholar.google.com>) is also considered. The first 100 search results, organized by relevance, are compared with search returns of the 5 previously cited databases. Articles returned by the Google Scholar search, but not found in the other databases searches, are added to the reference list.

3.1.3 Testing for performance of the search

A subset of meta-analyses on crop diversification were found by interviewing experts (see supplementary file). We assess whether these meta-analyses are also present in the list of references identified with the search equation.

3.1.4 Search terms, languages and restrictions

Sensitivity is favored over specificity. Sensitivity implies that the emphasis of the search procedure is put on collecting the largest selection of relevant articles at the risk of also obtaining a high number of non-relevant studies (hence increasing the duration of the screening step). Only studies published in English and in French are included, due to limited resources and the languages known by the study reviewers.

No date restriction is applied. All climatic zones are considered.

Our search terms consider the following list of intervention and population-related keywords:

For "Web of science" and "google scholar" database:

(meta-analysis OR meta analysis) AND (cropping system OR crop OR agriculture) AND ((rotation OR Diversification OR intercrop* OR cover crop OR mixture) OR (organic AND (system OR agriculture))) OR (conservation AND (system OR agriculture)) OR no till* OR agroforestry OR agroecology)*

For "Agricolae" database:

("meta-analysis" OR "meta analysis") AND ("cropping system" OR "crop?" OR "agriculture") AND (("rotation" OR "diversification" OR "intercrop?" OR "cover crop" OR "mixture") OR ("organic" AND ("system" OR "agriculture"))) OR ("conservation" AND ("system" OR "agriculture")) OR ("conservation" AND ("system" OR "agriculture")) OR ("no till?" OR "agroforestry" OR "agroecology")

CAB abstracts, Greenfile, and Environment Complete Databases were queries through ESBCO (<https://www.ebsco.com/>) search engine :

*First field : "meta-analysis" OR "meta analysis"
AND : "cropping system" OR "crop*" OR "agriculture"
AND : "rotation" OR "diversification" OR "intercrop*" OR "cover crop" OR "mixture"*

3.2 Inclusion criteria and article screening

3.2.1 Study inclusion and exclusion criteria

All meta-analyses are assessed for relevance using the following inclusion criteria:

- Relevance of the subject(s): Any meta-analysis investigating one or several strategies of crop diversification.
- Relevance of the study design considered in the meta-analyses: the study performed a meta-regression and/ or an estimation of a mean effect size.
- Relevance of the type of measured impacts: Production, environment, biodiversity or economic criteria
- Relevance of the comparator:

The soil characteristics and year of the control plot of all included individual studies are similar to those of the treatment plot. The control plot presents a lower level of diversification than the treatment plot.

We consider meta-analyses comparing cropping systems if they explicitly quantify the effect of crop diversification. We also consider meta-regressions if they cover a large range of diversified system.

3.2.2 Screening

A two steps screening process is performed. Titles and abstracts of all retrieve articles are screened, and then a full-text assessment is conducted. At each step, we check if the articles meet the inclusion criteria. In cases of doubt and in order to reduce the rate of false negative decisions, a second reviewer is asked to re-analyze all studies that do not clearly meet the inclusion criteria. Inconsistencies are discussed between the two reviewers.

The rejected studies are compiled in an exclusion database, with reasons for rejection.

3.3 Data extraction and analyses

3.3.1 Characteristics of the meta-analysis, potential effect modifiers and sources of heterogeneity

Meta-data (authors' names and affiliation, journal names, keywords, date of publication, large-scale region covered in the meta-analysis) are retrieved for all included meta-analyses. Study location or climatic conditions can increase the heterogeneity of the results. When mentioned in the studies, potential effect modifiers will be identified to better understand the variations of effects among studies. The factors are compiled in the quantitative database. A non-exhaustive list of potential effect modifiers is given hereafter:

- Location and years of the experiments of the primary studies included in the meta-analysis
- Environmental conditions, e.g. pedoclimatic conditions
- Type of methods used to synthesize primary studies (e.g. statistical method)

3.3.2 Study quality assessment

We define a set of criteria building up on a series of previous studies assessing the quality of meta-analyses (Philibert et al., 2012; Borenstein et al., 2011; Gates, 2002; Moher et al., 2009). The criteria are used to assess quality in all steps of the quantitative review process, i.e. literature search, data extraction, data analyses and interpretation. A special emphasis is given to the reproducibility of individual meta-analyses. Once collected, the information is used to score the quality of each meta-analysis.

3.3.3 Effect size and meta-regressors

We extract all the quantitative data related to the effects measured in the meta-analyses: effect, size, indicator of dispersion (confidence interval, and when applicable standard deviation or quantiles), significance (P-value) and number of data on which these effects are calculated. In the case of meta-regressions, we extract the estimated values of the intercept, the slope and information on their accuracy (i.e., confidence intervals).

3.3.4 Data extraction strategy

A single reviewer extracts all the data mentioned in the previous sections.

4 Data synthesis and presentation

All the information extracted from the meta-analysis (e.g., meta-data, quality analysis, effect size) is made available in a separate file. An analysis of the extracted effect sizes is carried out for each type of diversification separately. We also analyze possible relationships between the quality of the meta-analyses and their conclusions.

5 Declaration

Authors' contributions

This systematic review protocol was designed by DB, TBA, and DM. All authors read, corrected, and approved the final manuscript.

Acknowledgements

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests. If a reviewer is an author on a potentially relevant article, he or she will not be involved in the decisions regarding the inclusion of the article in the database.

Funding

This work was produced within the framework of the European project “Diversification through Rotation, Intercropping, Multiple Cropping, Promoted with Actors and value-Chains towards Sustainability” (DiverIMPACTS), funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement number 727482.

6 Supplementary file: list of pre-identified meta-analyses

1. Bowles, T. M., Jackson, L. E., Loeher, M., and Cavagnaro, T. R. (2017). Ecological intensification and arbuscular mycorrhizas: a meta-analysis of tillage and cover crop effects. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 54(6):1785–1793.
2. Iverson, A. L., Marn, L. E., Ennis, K. K., Gonthier, D. J., Connor-Barrie, B. T., Remfert, J. L., Cardinale, B. J., and Perfecto, I. (2014). Do polycultures promote win-wins or trade-offs in agricultural ecosystem services? a meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 51(6):1593–1602.
3. Kiaer, L. P., Skovgaard, I. M., and Ostergard, H. (2009). Grain yield increase in cereal variety mixtures: a meta-analysis of field trials. *Field Crops Research*, 114(3):361–373.
4. Letourneau, D. K., Armbrecht, I., Rivera, B. S., Lerma, J. M., Carmona, E. J., Daza, M. C., Escobar, S., Galindo, V., Gutierrez, C., Lopez, S. D., et al. (2011). Does plant diversity benefit agroecosystems? a synthetic review. *Ecological Applications*, 21(1):9–21.
5. Marcillo, G. and Miguez, F. (2017). Corn yield response to winter cover crops: An updated meta-analysis. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 72(3):226–239.
6. Miguez, F. E. and Bollero, G. A. (2005). Review of corn yield response under winter cover cropping systems using meta-analytic methods. *Crop Science*, 45(6):2318–2329.
7. Poeplau, C. and Don, A. (2015). Carbon sequestration in agricultural soils via cultivation of cover crops—a meta-analysis. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 200:33–41.
8. Pumarino, L., Sileshi, G. W., Gripenberg, S., Kaartinen, R., Barrios, E., Muchane, M. N., Midega, C., and Jonsson, M. (2015). Effects of agroforestry on pest, disease and weed control: a meta-analysis. *Basic and applied ecology*, 16(7):573–582.
9. Raseduzzaman, M. and Jensen, E. S. (2017). Does intercropping enhance yield stability in arable crop production? a meta-analysis. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 91:25–33.
10. Sileshi, G., Akinnifesi, F. K., Ajayi, O. C., and Place, F. (2008). Meta-analysis of maize yield response to woody and herbaceous legumes in sub-saharan africa. *Plant and soil*, 307(1-2):1–19.
11. Tonitto, C., David, M., and Drinkwater, L. (2006). Replacing bare fallows with cover crops in fertilizer- intensive cropping systems: A meta-analysis of crop yield and n dynamics. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 112(1):58–72.
12. Torralba, M., Fagerholm, N., Burgess, P. J., Moreno, G., and Plieninger, T. (2016). Do european agro- forestry systems enhance biodiversity and ecosystem services? a meta-analysis. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 230:150–161.
13. Valkama, E., Lemola, R., Kankanen, H., and Turtola, E. (2015). Meta-analysis of the effects of undersown catch crops on nitrogen leaching loss and grain yields in the nordic countries. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 203:93–101.
14. Venter, Z. S., Jacobs, K., and Hawkins, H.-J. (2016). The impact of crop rotation on soil

microbial diversity: A meta-analysis. *Pedobiologia*, 59(4):215–223.

15. Verret, V., Gardarin, A., Pelzer, E., Mediene, S., Makowski, D., and Valantin-Morison, M. (2017). Can legume companion plants control weeds without decreasing crop yield? a meta-analysis. *Field Crops Research*, 204:158–168.

16. Wei, H., Xiang, Y., Liu, Y., and Zhang, J. (2017). Effects of sod cultivation on soil nutrients in orchards across china: a meta-analysis. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 169:16–24.

References

Aguilar, J., Gramig, G. G., Hendrickson, J. R., Archer, D. W., Forcella, F., and Liebig, M. A. (2015). Crop species diversity changes in the united states: 1978–2012. *PloS one*, 10(8):e0136580.

Altieri, M. and Nicholls, C. (2004). *Biodiversity and pest management in agroecosystems*. CRC Press.

Altieri, M. A. (1999). The ecological role of biodiversity in agroecosystems. In *Invertebrate Biodiversity as Bioindicators of Sustainable Landscapes*, pages 19–31. Elsevier.

Bayala, J., Kalinganire, A., Sileshi, G., and Tondoh, J. (2018). Soil organic carbon and nitrogen in agroforestry systems in sub-saharan africa: A review. In *Improving the Profitability, Sustainability and Efficiency of Nutrients Through Site Specific Fertilizer Recommendations in West Africa Agro-Ecosystems*, pages 51–61. Springer.

Borenstein, M., Hedges, L. V., Higgins, J. P., and Rothstein, H. R. (2011). *Introduction to meta-analysis*. John Wiley & Sons.

Cernay, C., Makowski, D., and Pelzer, E. (2017). Preceding cultivation of grain legumes increases cereal yields under low nitrogen input conditions. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, pages 1–6.

Chen, H., Grieneisen, M. L., and Zhang, M. (2016). Predicting pesticide removal efficacy of vegetated filter strips: A meta-regression analysis. *Science of the Total Environment*, 548:122–130.

Gates, S. (2002). Review of methodology of quantitative reviews using meta-analysis in ecology. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, 71(4):547–557.

Gaudin, A. C., Tolhurst, T. N., Ker, A. P., Janovicek, K., Tortora, C., Martin, R. C., and Deen, W. (2015). Increasing crop diversity mitigates weather variations and improves yield stability. *PLoS One*, 10(2):e0113261.

Gurr, G. M., Wratten, S. D., and Luna, J. M. (2003). Multi-function agricultural biodiversity: pest management and other benefits. *Basic and Applied Ecology*, 4(2):107–116.

Kremen, C. and Miles, A. (2012). Ecosystem services in biologically diversified versus conventional farming systems: benefits, externalities, and trade-offs. *Ecology and Society*, 17(4).

Letourneau, D. K., Armbrrecht, I., Rivera, B. S., Lerma, J. M., Carmona, E. J., Daza, M. C., Escobar, S., Galindo, V., Gutiérrez, C., López, S. D., et al. (2011). Does plant diversity benefit agroecosystems? a synthetic review. *Ecological Applications*, 21(1):9–21.

Lin, B. B. (2011). Resilience in agriculture through crop diversification: adaptive management for environmental change. *BioScience*, 61(3):183–193.

- Miguez, F. E. and Bollero, G. A. (2005). Review of corn yield response under winter cover cropping systems using meta-analytic methods. *Crop Science*, 45(6):2318–2329.
- Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., Altman, D. G., Group, P., et al. (2009). Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the prisma statement. *PLoS medicine*, 6(7):e1000097.
- Philibert, A., Loyce, C., and Makowski, D. (2012). Assessment of the quality of meta-analysis in agronomy. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 148:72–82.
- Tengö, M. and Belfrage, K. (2004). Local management practices for dealing with change and uncertainty: a cross-scale comparison of cases in sweden and tanzania. *Ecology and Society*, 9(3).
- Tomich, T. P., Brodt, S., Ferris, H., Galt, R., Horwath, W. R., Kebreab, E., Leveau, J. H., Liptzin, D., Lubell, M., Merel, P., et al. (2011). Agroecology: a review from a global-change perspective. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 36:193–222.